

THE ROLE OF USING DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The digitalization of all aspects of our life today, including the role of digital technologies in the integration of preschool and primary education, the role of digital technologies in the training of future personnel, and the problems of modern education were seen in the article.

In the current conditions, a modern school needs teachers who have knowledge and skills in the use of information and communication technologies in their professional activities, and have well-formed information and communication competence (IEC). The use of digital technologies in the process of education and upbringing guarantees the achievements of children of preschool age, and the guarantees of successful studies at school later.

Currently, one of the directions of informatization of education is to create conditions for the subjects of the educational process, to facilitate the free use of information that is increasing in society: databases, electronic archives, reference books, encyclopedias, as well as active use of information and communication technologies in the process of forming the personality of students. In order to solve information problems, it is necessary to form the needs and possibilities of using information and communication technologies from childhood. Therefore, in our opinion, primary school is the main area of public information. In this regard, the professional competence of a modern primary school teacher includes special knowledge and skills in the collection, search, collection, storage, production, processing, transmission and use of information based on modern microprocessors and computers. It is impossible without skills. Thus, digital technologies should be an integral part of the competence of teachers to assess the quality of education. During the analysis, we identified the following contradictions: between the state and society's need for the formation of digital technologies of future teachers and the lack of comprehensive and experimental support for this process among elementary school teachers between the need to use information and communication technologies in their professional activities and the insufficient development of pedagogical conditions for their preparation at the stage of obtaining higher pedagogical education, the need to develop educational and methodological support of the educational

process in primary grades based on ICT and ' between the insufficient level of ATK of the primary school teachers.

These contradictions predetermine the relevance of learning to improve the competences of teachers of the future primary school "Science and Technology in the Modern World" scientific-practical conference, which we will consider. Today, along with developed countries, Uzbekistan is moving into the digital era, and the changes related to this are clearly visible in most cases, in the areas of production, housing and communal services, trade and other areas. Nowadays, we transfer the main part of our life to the virtual world: computer, laptop, tablet, smartphone and other devices. We chat, make friends, work, share photos, impressions, thoughts, play games, watch popular movies, click "likes", post information there. The penetration of information resources into the lives of all categories of citizens - from young children to pensioners - forms the opinion that information technologies are able to solve all the problems of modern society.

Modern digital technologies provide new tools for the development of all educational institutions around the world. Digitization creates opportunities to share lessons learned and knowledge, empowering people to be more informed and make better decisions in their daily lives. In the near future, there will be big changes in the educational environment related to digitization. The electronic education system creates new opportunities and new tasks in personnel training. The main opportunities include solving educational problems, expanding the choice of the form of education, and increasing the means of knowledge transfer. The need to understand the place and role of digital technologies in modern education should be reflected in modern research in the fields of preschool and primary education methodology and didactics. Currently, the problems of using digital technologies in the integration of preschool and primary education are the reason for research related to the choice of the future development strategy and direction. It is clear that a digital transformation program must already be developed in order to move to a competitive education and research model in the future.

Advantages of e-learning include:

- 1) Solving problems of access to education: elimination of territorial barriers to access to knowledge; removal of time restrictions - access at a convenient time for the user; the possibility of fractional access due to the division of classes into blocks; using the knowledge of highly qualified teachers.
- 2) widening the choice: the ability to choose the teacher and the method of presenting the material; focus on logic, imagery, or practice; the ability to choose the method of assimilation of material: through auditory, visual, motor skills or interactive participation; the ability to choose the depth of mastering the material - a wide range of courses; the ability to choose a convenient way to manage knowledge: tests, assignments, free essays, projects, interactive conversations with artificial intelligence, etc.
- 3) expansion of forms and means of knowledge transfer: in addition to traditional lectures, performances and seminars, the use of project work, group discussions, role-playing and competitive games, including with virtual participants, etc.

4) Socio-economic advantages: the possibility of forming social intellectual networks of interests; relative cheapness.

Traditional classroom instruction cannot provide a direct learning environment, faster assessment, and greater participation. Instead, digital learning tools and technology are filling the gap. As smartphones and other wireless technology devices become increasingly popular among the general public, schools and educational institutions can take advantage of them by introducing technology into the classroom. Our online class calendar, where we can display class schedules, assignment schedules, field trips, speaker events, exam schedules, or semester breaks, helps students plan accordingly. Integrating technology into education provides students with an engaging learning experience that allows them to engage more with the subject matter without distraction. The use of projectors, computers and other modern technologies in the classroom makes learning interesting for students. Student learning can be made more dynamic and engaging by using technology resources, oral presentations, and posing challenges that involve group participation in the classroom.

When digital technology is used in the classroom, children can become more engaged in their learning. Since today's youth are very accustomed to using electronic gadgets, including them in school education will surely arouse their interest and increase their level of activity. Integrating technology into education provides students with an engaging learning experience that allows them to engage more with the subject matter without distraction. The use of projectors, computers and other modern technologies in the classroom makes the learning process interesting and fun for students. Student learning becomes more dynamic and engaging by introducing technology resources, oral presentations, and group participation in the classroom.

Using computers and other devices alongside digital tools allows students to take a more active role and be at the center of the process. With access to a wide range of digital resources, students can download the information they need or upload their own content. Web 2.0 technologies (wikis, podcasts, blogs, etc.) help students create content, collaborate with others, evaluate each other's work, and learn together. Digital class. Digital classrooms are defined by the use of electronic devices or platforms such as social media, multimedia, and mobile phones for student learning.

Today's main problems that determine the low quality of the existing online education system are:

- the desire to imitate full-time education leads to the deterioration of the quality of the copy compared to the original. Digital imitation of traditional courses leads to the impoverishment of communication tools, the exclusion of forms of knowledge acquisition, such as personal processing of notes, assimilation of knowledge and discussion of controversial issues with the teacher.

The main threat of digitization of education for our country is to find the basis of the global educational environment. This threat can be realized as a result of several factors:

- delay in entering the world market;
- insufficient product quality;
- language barrier;

- the low rate of use of digital technologies by specialists of the primary education system;
- low level of language proficiency.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the introduction of digital technologies is very important for the development of the primary education system, but at the same time, it is necessary to form a scientifically based approach to their implementation.

Electronic multimedia lessons are provided in the form of an application to the elementary school textbooks of our schools, and they are used effectively in the lesson processes. The need to move to the digitalization of the educational space is explained by several factors. First, almost all students today belong to the digital native generation, and they show great inclination to use new technologies in their daily life. In particular, this applies to IT and Internet technologies, as well as their use not only in the professional sphere, but also for socialization and communication. In any case, if the correct use of modern pedagogical digital technologies guarantees the success of children of primary school age, then it guarantees their successful studies in higher grades.

Thus, the use of the digital education system serves as a basis for primary education students to become members of the target audience for entering the digital society in the future. This, of course, will increase the school's competitiveness in the educational market, create added value and attract children. First of all, it increases competitiveness; Secondly, it adapts the educational process to the world standard. In such conditions, personality formation is fundamentally different from the previous traditional methods, which requires the development of a qualitatively new model of its implementation in the integration of preschool primary education in the globalized information space, completely new methods that are necessary and suitable for the current conditions. It requires the formation of methodical works that include it. In any case, the correct use of modern pedagogical digital technologies guarantees the achievements of children of preschool and primary education age and their successful studies in higher grades.

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